

ONUS OF CLASSROOM LEADERS: HOW ERUDITION DEVELOPS BY GIVING AND RECEIVING PEER PARTICIPATION

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Received: 2019-01-10

Accepted: 2019-03-05

Published online: 2019-03-21

Abstract

Leadership is a natural ability to lead a group of individuals to translate vision into reality. The researchers used the mixed method research through the online checklist. In gathering reliable information, the researchers adopted questionnaires from the research entitled Onus of Classroom Leaders: How Erudition Develops by Giving and Receiving Peer Participation. The researchers use also cell phone for the documentation specially in making screenshot of the online feedback. Based on the table the researcher used a conceptual framework to elaborate the classroom leadership skills and teaching and learning process where strategies used as a key elements to state and phrase the findings and result hence the researcher proposed to used this in LFG DIAMANTINA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL as a basis to create intervention and output based education in terms of doing so. This is based on their raw score from a 30-item test in each of the qualities of classroom leaders. Also, it indicates that the learners are interestingly good enough to further experience leadership capabilities of the students. Both post-test mean scores of the groups lie between 19–24 score interval. This means they got “high” scores in the 30-item test in each of the Qualities of a good leader. However, leadership skills can earn through a harmonious relationship between the two.

Introduction

Students are composed of different behavior that you can encounter in school. Some of them are responsible in their life especially in their role as a student and role as a leader. Being a leader in school has a big role because you need to become a good model to your fellow students. Leader is not about being in a position, but it is all about the responsibility. Leadership is a natural ability to lead a group of individuals to translate vision into reality. One who retains leadership is one who knows and shows the way to synthesize blueprints. We do actions to achieve the greatest extent of victory.

The world dominated by humans demand a leader behind the prevalence of turbulence, and proliferation of unfortunate rates of bad humanity. In spite of these circumstances, leader sets aside a vision for the evolution in all aspects, mostly to the promotion of Teaching & Learning relationship for a dynamic education.

Great leaders possess dazzling social intelligence, a zest for change, and above all a vision that allows them to set their sights on the things that truly merit attention. Not a bad skill set for the rest of entity, either. I

It is the job of leaders to develop a vision-establish what matters and articulate why-set direction, and inspire others. Recent research on the skill leaders need establishes the increasing importance of inner resources of the psyche such as self-awareness and self-mastery. (Psychology Today)

Scope and Delimitation

The purpose of this study is to determine the Onus of Classroom Leaders: How Erudition Develops by Giving and Receiving Peer Participation. The study was conducted via online questionnaire among the students of Quirino NHS, Monico Rarama NHS and Diamantina NHS.

The respondents were Grade 7 to Grade 12 officers with the number of 102 students by using the purposive sampling.

Materials and Methodology

This chapter presents the methodology, the respondents, the data gathering instruments and procedures and the statistical tools that were used in analyzing and interpreting the needed data in attaining the objectives of the study.

Methods of research used

In order to determine the effectiveness of Onus of Classroom Leaders: How Erudition Develops by Giving and Receiving Peer Participation then researchers used the mixed method research through the online checklist.

Instruments used in the study

In order to gathered reliable information, the researchers adopted questionnaires from the research entitled Onus of Classroom Leaders: How Erudition Develops by Giving and Receiving Peer Participation. The researchers use also cell phone for the documentation specially in making screenshot of the online feedback.

Data Gathering Procedures

In securing the most needed data, the following activities were undertaken by the researchers.

1. Asked permission from the principal and community to conduct the study.
2. Online survey questionnaires to the respondent
3. Collect the data;
4. Retrieved the feedback;
5. Tabulated the data gathered ; and
6. Interpret and analyze the data gathered.

Statistical tools be used

In order to analyze the data gathered for this study; researchers will made use of the following statistical tools:

1. Frequency and percentage distribution for the profile of the respondents.
2. Mean formula to add up all the numbers then divide by the number of numbers.

3. After the retrieval, the data will be tallied, tabulated, and computed to facilitate the analysis and interpretation of data. The following statistical tools will be used: **T-test-** A t-test's statistical significance indicates whether or not the difference between two groups' averages most likely reflects a "real" difference in the population from which the groups are sampled.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter examines the results and discussions of the Onus of Classroom Leaders: How Erudition Develops by Giving and Receiving Peer Participation Leadership Skills Framework:

Based on the table the researcher used a conceptual framework to elaborate the duties of leadership skills as a basis to create intervention and output based education in terms of doing a concrete projects or programs in the **Department of Education** not only in the Province of Isabela but nationwide.

First Test Marks

The pretest scores of the students from the thirty-item test in leadership test in each presented in Table 1. *Summary of First Test Marks in the Classroom Leaders and Teacher and Student Leadership among online students of QNHS, MNHS and DNHS.*

Qualities of Leader	CLASSROOM LEADERS		TEACHER & STUDENT RELATIONSHIP	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Dedication	7.20	Low	8.95	Low
Passion	8.65	Low	9.20	Low
Time	9.20	Low	8.30	Low
ProblemSolve	8.40	Low	8.85	Low
r	10.25	Low	9.55	Low
Open-Minded				

Note: Very High (25-30), High (19-24), Fair (13-18), Low (7-12), Very Low (0-6)

Table 1 shows that the Duties or Onus of Classroom Leaders has a descriptive statistics of good. And since both groups have not received any treatment or lesson discussions yet, they obtained the same “low” mean scores which fall between 7 – 12 intervals. This is based on their raw score from a 30-item test in each of the qualities of classroom leaders. Also, it indicates that the learners are interestingly good enough to further experience leadership capabilities of the students.

Second Test Marks

Summary of second Test Marks in the Classroom Leaders and Teacher and Student Leadership among online students of QNHS, MNHS and DNHS.

Qualities of Leader	CLASSROOM LEADERS		TEACHER & STUDENT RELATIONSHIP	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Dedication	21.10	High	19.65	High
Passion	20.75	High	19.40	High
Time	22.20	High	21.40	High
ProblemSolve	18.00	High	20.30	High
r	15.25	High	19.35	High
Open-Minded				

Note: Very High (25-30), High (19-24), Fair (13-18), Low (7-12), Very Low (0-6)

Table 2 shows the second test marks between the CL and TL groups. Both second test marks of the groups lie between 19 – 24 score interval. This means they got “high” scores in the 30-item test in each of the Qualities of a good leader. However, leadership skills can earn through a harmonious relationship between leader and follower.

Table 3

Summary of t-values for the Test of Significance of Mean Difference in the Classroom Leadership Skill and Teacher and Student Relationship.

Qualities of Leader	CLASSROOM LEADERS		Mean Difference	T-Value	P-Value
	First Test Marks	Second Test Marks			
Dedication	9.10	19.15	10.05	- 17.67***	0.00000000000003
Passion	9.75	19.45	9.70	- 19.91***	0.00000000000003
Time	9.00	20.25	11.25	- 20.75***	0.00000000000002
Problem Solver	8.40	19.70	11.30	- 17.40***	0.00000000000004
Open-Minded	10.25	21.65	11.40	- 18.34***	0.00000000000002

*Note: The *** indicates that the result is highly significant, while * is significant. Critical Value: 2.100312*

Table 3 shows that the mean difference first and second test marks of students are highly significant. Conclusively, students excel farther in viewing skill when Classroom leaders are active. With mean difference of 11.4, this proves that students can improve their receptive skills in leadership (Lightbown, 2010). Also, time bound with t-value of -17.67 means “highly significant” and with mean difference of 9.7 against problem solver skill because it entails that they are eager to listen.

On the other hand, dedication as a leader has a mean difference of 11.3 while passion has a mean difference of 11.25 against problem solver. The result above is supported with the study of Joshua Bolkan (2017), an online survey administered to 250 classroom leaders in the United States showed that 56% have seen student improvement in their qualities as classroom leaders.

Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations Summary

Based on the research the researcher proved that CLASSROOM LEADERSHIP SKILLS AMONG JHS & SHS STUDENTS: EVALUATION IN PROMOTING TEACHING AND LEARNING is an action to adapt and disseminate the information the following statement is the summary of the findings: Based on the table the researcher used a conceptual framework to elaborate the classroom leadership skills and teaching and learning process where strategies used as a key elements to state and phrase the findings and result hence the researcher proposed to used this in LFG DIAMANTINA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL as a basis to create intervention and output based education in terms of doing so. This is based on their raw score from a 30-item test in each of the qualities of classroom leaders. Also, it indicates that the learners are interestingly good enough to further experience leadership capabilities of the students. Both post-tests mean scores of the groups lie between 19 – 24 score interval. This means they got “high” scores in the 30-item test in each of the Qualities of a good leader. However, leadership skills can earn through a harmonious relationship between the two.

CONCLUSIONS

This research paper highlights the vital role of classroom leaders in assessing the students’ and teacher leadership. The following are the conclusions based on the findings of the study:

1. Classroom leadership’s skills among DepEd Secondary school in District 2. Generally, CL and TL helps in increasing the academic performance of the learners since teachers is the key role is used as an intervention and motivation to learners.
2. Students leadership skills have relationship to each other and superior against passion and dedication. These three skills are receptive or input skills. Therefore, they involve similar thinking processes for decoding skills and learning.
3. Students indicate that the learners are interestingly good enough to further experience leadership capabilities of the students as table 1 shown. There are really those who excel in qualities of leaders.
4. Students’ performance is highly dependent on the type of teachers teaching used in the teaching-learning process.
5. The significant relationship in dedication as a leader has a mean difference of 11.3 while passion has a mean difference of 11.25 against problem solver. The result above is supported with the study of Joshua Bolkan (2017), an online survey administered to 250 classroom leaders in the United States showed that 56% have seen student improvement in their qualities as classroom leaders.

Recommendations

Based on the results in the conduct of this study, the researcher suggests the following statements:

1. Teachers should equally provide the students with repertoire of activities;
2. In preparing an activity make it sure that students is promoting and creating themselves as individual and group leader;
3. Dedication and Discipline skills of learners should be enhanced with more exposure to seminars and trainings orientation;
4. Teachers may attend workshops and seminars to keep updated on the trends in teaching leadership.

Acknowledgment

The researchers would like to acknowledge Local Government Unit of Quirino and principals who sponsor for funding the study.

References

- Adodo, S., & Agbayewa, J. O. (2011). Effect of homogenous and heterogeneous ability grouping class teaching on student's interest, attitude and achievement in integrated science. *International Journal of Psychology and Counselling, 3*(3), 48-54.
- Bamberger, M., Rao, V., & Woolcock, M. (2010). Using mixed methods in monitoring and evaluation: Experiences from international development. In A. Tashakkori. & C. Teddlie (Eds.), *Sage handbook of mixed methods in social & behavioral research* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Blumenfeld, P. C., Marx, R. W., Soloway, E., & Krajcik, J. (1996). Learning with peers: From small group cooperation to collaborative communities. *Educational Researcher, 25*(8), 37-40.
- Carolan, B. V. (2012). *Social network analysis and education: Theory, methods & applications*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Chi, M. T. (1997). Quantifying qualitative analyses of verbal data: A practical guide. *Journal of the Learning Sciences, 6*(3), 271-315. Chi, M. T., Siler, S. A., & Jeong, H. (2004).
- Cho, K., & MacArthur, C. (2010). Student revision with peer and expert reviewing. *Learning and Instruction, 20*(4), 328-338.
- Wu, A., Farrell, R., & Singley, M. (2002, Jan 7-11). *Scaffolding group learning in a collaborative networked environment*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of CSCL 2002, Colorado.
- Xiao, Y., & Lucking, R. (2008). The impact of two types of peer assessment on students' performance and satisfaction within a Wiki environment. *The Internet and Higher Education, 11*(3-4), 186-193.